

IRON-IRON OXIDE ELECTRODE FOR ACID-BASE POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATIONS AND FOR H-ION CONCENTRATION DETERMINATION.

BY BHARAT RAM AGARWAL AND J. B. JHA.

Iron electrode was tried by McAulay and White (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 194) for the determination of H⁺ ion concentration. His results were irregular especially beyond p_H 7 i.e., in the alkaline solutions.

As iron is one of those elements not attacked by alkalis, it was thought desirable to study the same for its use in alkaline as well as acidic solutions. The electrodes studied were really iron-iron oxide electrodes prepared by various methods. Those found more satisfactory are given below :—

(i) Iron oxide was deposited on a mild steel wire by treating it with fuming nitric acid (d 1.4) and subsequently boiling with distilled water for an hour and keeping in dilute acetic acid for a day. The electrode prepared in this way attained a steady potential within a few minutes when placed in a $M/5$ -potassium hydrogen phthalate solution. To maintain the potential the wire was left in dilute acetic acid which was found to be quite satisfactory.

TABLE I.

Time.	E. M. F.	Time.	E. M. F.	Remarks.
0 min.	-0.635 volts	20 min.	-0.641	Electrode attains stability in about two minutes.
2	-0.640	30	-0.641	
5	-0.641	60	-0.641	
10	-0.641	120	-0.641	

Titration curves with a buffer solution (Britton and Robinson straight line buffer) are shown in Fig. 1.

Acid base titrations can be easily performed by iron-iron oxide electrode as an indicating electrode. E. M. F. changes along with burette readings are shown in Fig. 2. It may be noted that the alkaline solution was added from the burette so that the electrode was always in contact with an acidic solution throughout the titration.

Another electrode that was tried and found satisfactory was prepared by depositing iron electrolytically on a platinum wire from an iron ammonium citrate solution. The deposited layer was oxidised by

putting it in strong nitric acid for five minutes and then washed with distilled water.

The titration curves (i) with Britton and Robinsons' straight line buffer solution and (ii) acid base titrations are shown in Figs. 3 and 4.

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3*

FIG. 4*

It is noteworthy that the titration curves show a break in the neighbourhood of p_H 7 in both the cases.

The relationships observed from a large number of titrations for a mild steel wire oxidised with (i) nitric acid and (ii) electrolytically deposited iron over platinum wire are given below

$$E_1 = -0.4965 - 0.0383 (p_H) \text{ at } 25^\circ. \quad E_2 = +0.527 - 0.0714 (p_H) \text{ at } 25^\circ$$

$$E_3 = -0.721 - 0.0061 (p_H) \text{ at } 25^\circ. \quad E_4 = +0.237 - 0.0337 (p_H) \text{ at } 25^\circ.$$

The end-point in acid base titrations was shown by a break in the curve and not by an inflexion point.

In alkaline solutions the electrode is not of much use.

Our thanks are due to Principal H. Krall and Prof. B. L. Vaish for their active interest in the work.